

Full Translation: Physiological Evaluation of Heat Tolerance in Winter Soft Wheat Varieties and Their F₀ Hybrids

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Relevance of the Topic

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is one of the most widely cultivated cereal crops and plays an important role in ensuring global food security. It ranks second only to rice among cereal crops [1]. Wheat is a temperate crop and sensitive to high temperature: for every 2°C increase above 18°C, its potential yield decreases by about 10% [2]. Wheat is a good source of carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals. It contains more protein than other cereals, making it a primary source of plant-based protein worldwide.

Annual global wheat consumption increases by 2%, necessitating the development of high-yielding and disease-resistant varieties. Genetic research on wheat has provided useful data for breeding higher-yielding and better-quality varieties [3]. With increasing interest in healthy food, nutritional modification (combination, fermentation, fortification) has attracted attention. Wheat is important in human nutrition and rich in nutrients such as minerals, protein (8%–16%), fat (1%–3%), and fiber (12%–15%) [4].

High temperature affects various physiological, biological, and biochemical processes in wheat [5]. Heat stress is one of the most frequent abiotic stresses and poses a serious threat to yield [6]. It leads to poor germination, shorter grain-filling duration, reduced grain number, decreased photosynthesis and assimilation rates, early leaf senescence, and reduced chlorophyll content. It also adversely affects the starch and protein content of the grain [7].

In our laboratory experiments, we evaluated the physiological heat tolerance of winter soft wheat varieties and the F₀ hybrids obtained through crossbreeding.

Research Methods and Materials

In the experiments, five leaves from F₀ hybrid samples obtained through crossbreeding were placed in a water bath at 40°C for 30 minutes. Then, one leaf from each sample was transferred to a Petri dish filled with cold water. Next, the water bath temperature was increased to 50°C, and after 10 minutes, a second leaf was placed in cold water. This process continued up to 80°C.

After the heat treatments, all samples were placed in Petri dishes containing 0.2N hydrochloric acid (HCl) for 20 minutes. Leaf damage was assessed using F.F. Matskov's method [8], where the appearance of brown spots indicates damage level:

- no brown spots = “–”
- less than 50% of surface = “+”
- more than 50% of surface = “++”
- fully covered = “+++”

The studied wheat varieties were Karavan, Ultra, Grom, ASR, Vassa, and Krasnodarskaya-99.

Results and Their Analysis.

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Under different temperature conditions, the degree of leaf damage in wheat variety samples and F₀ hybrid samples obtained through crossbreeding was studied by classifying them into three groups (tolerant, moderately tolerant, and susceptible) (Tables 1 and 2).

At 40°C, no damage was observed in the leaf samples of the studied varieties.

Table 1.

Damage degree of wheat variety leaves under different temperatures

No	Variety Name	Degree of leaf damage under different temperatures				
		40°C	50°C	60°C	70°C	80°C
Tolerant						
1	Karavan	-	-	+	++	++
2	Ultra	-	-	+	++	+++
Moderately tolerant						
3	Grom	-	-	++	++	++
Susceptible						
4	Krasnodarskaya-99	-	+	++	+++	+++
5	Vassa	-	+	+++	+++	+++

At 50°C, the leaves of Karavan, Ultra, and Grom variety samples were undamaged, while the leaves of Krasnodarskaya-99 and Vassa varieties were damaged by less than 50% with brown spots.

At 60°C, the leaves of Karavan and Ultra varieties were damaged by less than 50% with brown spots, while those of Grom and Krasnodarskaya-99 varieties were damaged by more than 50%. It was observed that only the leaf surface of the Vassa variety was completely covered with brown spots.

At 70°C, the leaves of the variety samples were more than 50% and fully covered with brown spots. The varieties with more than 50% but not fully damaged leaves included Karavan, Ultra, and Grom. The leaves of Krasnodarskaya-99 and Vassa varieties were found to be completely covered with brown spots.

Table 2.

Damage degree of F₀ hybrid leaves under different temperatures

No	F ₀ Hybrid Name	Degree of leaf damage under different temperatures				
		40°C	50°C	60°C	70°C	80°C
Tolerant						

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1	Karavan × Vassa	-	-	++	++	+++
Moderately tolerant						
2	Vassa × Krasnodarskaya-99	-	+	++	+++	+++
3	Karavan × Ultra	-	+	+++	+++	+++
Susceptible						
4	Karavan × Krasnodarskaya-99	-	++	+++	+++	+++
5	Vassa × Karavan	+	++	++	+++	+++
6	Vassa × Grom	++	+++	+++	+++	+++

At 40°C, among the F₀ hybrids obtained from the studied crosses, the leaves of the hybrids Karavan × Vassa, Vassa × Krasnodarskaya-99, Karavan × Ultra, and Karavan × Krasnodarskaya-99 were found to be undamaged. Meanwhile, the hybrid Vassa × Karavan was damaged by brown spots by less than 50%, and the hybrid Vassa × Grom showed damage by brown spots exceeding 50%.

At 50°C, the leaves of the hybrid Karavan × Vassa were undamaged, while the hybrids Vassa × Krasnodarskaya-99 and Karavan × Ultra were damaged by brown spots by less than 50%. The hybrids Karavan × Krasnodarskaya-99 and Vassa × Karavan showed damage by brown spots exceeding 50%. Only the hybrid Vassa × Grom had its leaf surface completely covered with brown spots.

At 60°C, the hybrids Karavan × Vassa, Vassa × Krasnodarskaya-99, and Vassa × Karavan were found to be damaged by brown spots by more than 50%. All other hybrids had their leaf surfaces completely covered with brown spots.

At 70°C, the hybrid Karavan × Vassa showed damage by brown spots exceeding 50%, while the leaf surfaces of all other hybrids were completely covered with brown spots.

At 80°C, all hybrids were 100% damaged.

Conclusions.

At 40°C, no leaf damage was observed in any wheat variety. At 70–80°C, leaves of Krasnodarskaya-99 and Vassa were fully covered with brown spots. At 80°C, Grom and Karavan leaves showed more than 50% but not complete damage, indicating physiological heat tolerance.

Among the F₀ hybrids, Karavan × Vassa was heat-tolerant; Vassa × Krasnodarskaya-99 and Karavan × Ultra were moderately tolerant; Karavan × Krasnodarskaya-99, Vassa × Karavan, and Vassa × Grom were susceptible.

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